

Spectrophotometric Studies on the Nature of the Decomposition Product of Ethereal Blue Chromium Peroxychromate

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ALTHOUGH many attempts¹⁻⁵ have been made in the past to study the decomposition product of the ethereal blue chromium peroxychromate, no conclusive evidence for the nature of the actual product of decomposition in water has been forthcoming. An attempt has been made in the present communication to show from spectrophotometric studies that the said decomposition product in water is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$.

Experimental

The blue compound was prepared in the usual way³, the extraction being done in ether. Then, 50 ml of the blue compound was decomposed in 200 ml of distilled water free from reducing substances. The decomposition product (aqueous layer) was separated for the following spectrophotometric studies.

Estimation of Cr(VI) and Cr(III) in the Decomposition Product: The recommended procedure⁶ for the estimation of Cr(VI) spectrophotometrically is from the absorption studies of Cr(VI) complex with 1-5 diphenylcarbazide. Thus, by complexing the Cr(VI) of the decomposition product in water with diphenylcarbazide and noting its absorption, the concentration of Cr(VI) was ascertained from the calibration curve drawn for known concentrations of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions. Next, the Cr(III) of the decomposition product was oxidised as per the procedure recommended by Oelschlayer⁷ and the increased total concentration of Cr(VI) was similarly determined. Obviously the rise in concentration of Cr(VI) corresponded to the amount of Cr(III) originally present in the decomposition product. It was found that the amount of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) in the decomposition product was in 1 : 3 ratio. The Beer's law graph has been excluded for the sake of brevity.

From the knowledge of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ion concentration the absorption spectra of the decomposition product in water was compared with that of a solution of potassium dichromate of equal strength. There was great similarity between the two absorption curves, with maxima lying at 360 nm and 440 nm in the case of the water decomposition product.

Thus from the ratio between Cr(III) and Cr(VI) and the absorption spectra it can be concluded that the decomposition product in water of the blue chromium peroxychromate extracted with ether is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$.

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Polarographic Reduction of Indium (III) in 2,2' Dimercapto Diethyl Ether Media

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THIS communication reports the polarographic reduction of In^{3+} in 2,2' dimercapto diethyl ether, determination, of its kinetic parameters at various concentrations of ligand and temperatures and the values of thermodynamic functions for the electrode reaction.

2,2' dimercapto diethyl ether (referred herein as $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$) was supplied by Evan's Chemicals, Inc., N.Y., and other chemicals were of Anal-R (BDH) grade. The entire study was carried out in 40% ethanolic media at $\text{pH} = 4.0$ and ionic strength $\mu = 0.1M$. NaClO_4 and Triton X-100 were used as supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor respectively. The capillary of the manual polarograph had the following characteristics, $m = 2.652$ mg/sec, $t = 2.65$ sec, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.253$ $\text{mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/2}$. The experimental procedure and the methods adopted have been described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

$\text{In}(\text{III})$ ions produced cathodic waves in presence of 2,2' dimercapto diethyl ether. The plots of $\log i/i_a - i$ vs. E_{de} for the waves were straight lines but their slopes were not in agreement to the theoretical values indicating the irreversible nature of the

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